

TRANSIENT TEMPERATURE FIELD AND INDUCED INTERLAMINAR STRESSES
OF REVOLUTIONARY LAMINATED COMPOSITE SHELLS*

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates transient temperature variations along the thickness of revolutionary laminated composite shells under various types of heat conductive boundary conditions and induced interlaminar stresses by using the quasi-3D finite element method. The heat capacity matrix lumping technique is successfully employed to improve the accuracy of the transient temperature field analysis. The temperature-dependent thermo-physical and mechanical properties are considered. The effects of the ply orientation and the stacking sequence on the distribution of the transient temperature and induced interlaminar stresses are included in the formulation. Results are presented for a $[\pm 45]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminated composite cylindrical shell. Certain conclusions have been drawn from these results.

KEYWORDS: Composite; Laminated Shell; Edge effect; Transient temperature field; Finite element analysis.

1. Introduction

The response of a laminated composite structure near its free edges has been a subject of intensive investigation during the past two decades. The interlaminar stress problem due to mechanical loading is well studied [1-6]. Owing to the inherent complexity in dealing with the interlaminar stress analysis caused by thermal loading, however, only a very limited number of solutions are available up to date. A.S.D wang and F.W. Crossman [7] examined the edge stresses in the laminates under uniform thermal loadings; H.R. Chen and Y.B. Shi [8] studied the edge effects in axisymmetric revolutionary laminated composite shells under uniform and nonuniform thermal loadings in the steady state case. There has few

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reports in the open literature of study on the problem of transient temperature field and induced interlaminar stresses.

The purpose of this paper is to examine the transient temperature field and predict the interlaminar stresses near the free edge region for revolutionary laminated composite bodies/shells under various types of heat conductive boundary conditions. Two aspects are presented in the paper. At first, the formulae of a kind of quasi-3D isoparametric element based on anisotropic heat conductive theory and thermoelasticity are derived and a new heat capacity matrix lumping technique is developed. Secondly, we examine the effect of transient heating upon the characteristics of temperature field and the nature of the interlaminar stress distribution in the vicinity of the free edge in the laminated composite shells. Numerical results for $[\pm 45]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminated composite cylindrical shell are given. Certain conclusions are drawn, which would enable us to get a better understanding of the fundamental nature of transient temperature and free edge effects and provide some effective measures to improve the loading capability of laminated composite shells. The present approach and computer code are also applicable to with the analysis of revolutionary bodies/shells under mechanical and thermal combined loads, and/or curing process.

2. Thermal Conductive Formulation

A revolutionary laminated composite shell is shown in Fig.1. According to

FIGURE 1. Geometry of laminated composite circular cylindrical shell

FIGURE 2. A new heat capacity matrix scheme

the variational principle, a functional representation which describes the transient heat conduction under various types of temperature boundary conditions can be expressed as:

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_a^b \int_0^R [\lambda_x \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \lambda_z \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z}\right)^2 + 2\rho C_v \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - 2QT](z+R) dx dz \quad (1)$$

$$+ \int_{S_2} qT ds + \int_{S_3} \frac{h}{2} (T^2 - 2TT_\infty) ds$$

where λ_x and λ_z are the transformed thermal conductivities in the x and z

directions, respectively; Q is the internal heat generation per unit volume; q is the density of heat input; h is the convective heat transfer coefficient; T_∞ is the convective medium temperature; ρ and C_p are the density and heat capacity, respectively, and R is the radius of the revolutionary shell.

Within the domain $\Omega^{(e)}$ for each element, the temperature field is assumed as:

$$T = [N]\{T\}^{(e)} \quad (2)$$

in which $[N]$ is the element shape function matrix, $\{T\}^{(e)}$ is the element nodal temperature vector.

Substituting Eq.2 into Eq.1 and subsequently taking variation with respect to the nodal temperature vector $\{T\}^{(e)}$, we have the following discrete thermal equilibrium equation:

$$[K]\{T\}^{(e)} + [C]\left\{\frac{\partial T}{\partial t}\right\}^{(e)} = \{R\} \quad (3)$$

where $[K]$, $[C]$ and $\{R\}$ are conductive matrix, consistent capacity matrix and heat load vector of the element, respectively; and can be evaluated by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} [K] &= \int_{\Omega^{(e)}} [B]^T [\lambda] [B] (R+z) dx dz + \int_{S_3} [N]^T [N] h ds \\ [C] &= \int_{\Omega^{(e)}} \rho C_p [N]^T [N] dx dz \\ \{R\} &= \int_{\Omega^{(e)}} Q [N]^T (R+z) dx dz + \int_{S_3} [N]^T h T_\infty ds - \int_{S_2} [N]^T q ds \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $[B]$ is the nodal temperature-gradient matrix.

In order to ensure integral process with respect to time field to possess nonconditional stability, the backward difference scheme is adopted, letting

$$\left\{\frac{\partial T}{\partial t}\right\}_t^{(e)} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} (\{T\}_t^{(e)} - \{T\}_{t-\Delta t}^{(e)}) \quad (5)$$

in which Δt denotes the incremental time step. Substitution of Eq.5 into Eq.3 yields:

$$([K] + \frac{1}{\Delta t} [C])\{T\}_t^{(e)} = \{R\}_t - \frac{1}{\Delta t} [C]\{T\}_{t-\Delta t}^{(e)} \quad (6)$$

In addition, to avoid the "jumping" and "shifting" error and improve the integral accuracy for analyzing the transient temperature field a new capacity matrix lumping scheme, as shown in Fig.2, is employed, instead of the above consistent capacity matrix scheme. The new scheme has been applied successfully to the transient heat conductive problems of the

composite laminates by the same authors [9].

3. Thermal Stress Formulation

The potential energy function for a revolutionary laminated composite shell subjected to the thermal loading case is

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \{(\varepsilon) - \{\bar{\alpha}\} \Delta T\}^T \{\sigma\} (R+z) dx dz \quad (7)$$

in which $\{\varepsilon\}$ and $\{\sigma\}$ are the total strain vector and the total mechanical stress vector, respectively; ΔT is the temperature increment, and $\{\bar{\alpha}\}$ are the transformed thermal expansion coefficients of the lamina. Assuming each lamina to be transversely isotropic. Constitutive relationship for each lamina is given by:

$$\{\sigma\} = [\bar{Q}] \{(\varepsilon) - \{\bar{\alpha}\} \Delta T\} \quad (8)$$

where $[\bar{Q}]$ is the transformed stiffness matrix of the lamina.

The strain-displacement relations of the revolutionary shell is written as:

$$\{\varepsilon\} = [L] \{u\} \quad (9)$$

where $[L]$ is an operator matrix [8], and $\{u\} = \{u \ v \ w\}^T$ is the displacement vector.

Within a domain $\Omega^{(e)}$ for each element, the displacement field is assumed in the following form:

$$\{u\} = [N] \{\delta\}^{(e)} \quad (10)$$

where $[N]$ is the element shape function matrix, $\{\delta\}^{(e)}$ is the element nodal displacement vector.

Substituting Eq.10 into Eq.9 the relation of the strain-nodal displacement of the element can be obtained as:

$$\{\varepsilon\} = [L][N] \{\delta\}^{(e)} = [B] \{\delta\}^{(e)} \quad (11)$$

where $[B]$ is the strain-nodal displacement matrix of the element.

Furthermore, substituting Eq.8 and Eq.11 into Eq.7 and subsequently varying with respect to the nodal displacement vector, we have the following discrete equilibrium equation:

$$[K] \{\delta\}^{(e)} = \{R\} \quad (12)$$

where $[K]$ and $\{R\}$ are the stiffness matrix and thermal load vector of the element, respectively, which expressions are given by

$$[K] = \int_{\Omega^{(e)}} [B]^T [\bar{Q}] [B] (R+z) dx dz$$

$$\{R\} = \int_{\Omega^{(e)}} [B]^T [Q] \{\alpha\} \Delta T (R+z) dx dz \tag{13}$$

4. Numerical Example

Consider a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminated composite circular cylindrical shell as shown in Fig.1. The ratio of radius of the midsurface to the thickness of the shell is 20. The temperature at the inner surface and outer surface of the shell increases from the initial temperature 0°C to 250°C and 20°C , respectively. The effect of variation of material properties with respect to the temperature is taken into account. The values of material properties used here are taken from Ref.[10].

Fig.3 shows the temperature distributions along the thickness of the shell for various time interval. It is obvious that the transient temperature gradients are relatively large in the vicinity of the heated boundary. Before the heat conduction reaches the steady state, the temperature gradient decreases with the distance from the heated boundary. The closer the distance, the larger the temperature gradient, and vice versa. However, when the heat conduction reaches the steady state, the temperature gradients along the thickness of the shell become constant approximately.

Fig.4 illustrates the temperature variations with time interval at the various position of the thickness. The curves given in the figure show that the histories of the temperature variation with time at the boundary points

FIGURE 3. Temperature distribution along the thickness of the shell in various time interval

FIGURE 4. Temperature variations with time interval at the various position

are different from those of the points of the internal boundary. The temperature variation rate at $Z/h=-3/8$ rises sharply in the first 5 seconds, and then appears to be gently. However, the temperature variation

rate at $Z/h=-1/4$ appears to be slow from 0.0 to 1.0 Sec., then it becomes apparently fast from 1.0 to 5.0 Sec., and slow afterwards. A similar phenomenon is observed from the curve at $Z/h=-1/8$.

Fig.5 and 6 represent the distributions of the interlaminar normal stress σ_z and shear stress τ_{xz} and $Z/h=-0.25$ ($\pm 45^\circ$ interface) respectively. The solid lines denote the transient solutions at $t=10.0$ Sec. and dashed lines are the solutions in the steady state. The value of maximum transient compressive stress σ_z is about 3.5 times of the corresponding value in the steady state. The maximum transient tensile stress occurs at $x/h=0.333$ and

FIGURE 5. Distribution of σ_z at $Z/h=-0.25$ ($\pm 45^\circ$ interface)

FIGURE 6. Distribution of τ_{xz} at $Z/h=-0.25$ ($\pm 45^\circ$ interface)

is about 1.33 times of that for the steady state. The peak value of τ_{xz} also occurs at $x/h=0.333$ and is about 1.7 times of that for the corresponding steady state.

Fig.7 and 8 respectively represent distributions of σ_z and τ_{xz} along the thickness at $x/L=0.4917$ (near the free edge). It should be noted from the

FIGURE 7. Distribution of σ_z along the thickness at $X/L=0.4917$

FIGURE 8. Distribution of τ_{xz} along the thickness at $X/L=0.4917$

curves in these figures that not only the peak value but also temperature gradients of σ_z and τ_{xz} along-the thickness in transient state are quite larger than that in the steady state.

5. Concluding Remarks

From the above numerical analysis, the following conclusions may be drawn;

1. The gradient of temperature variation through the thickness of the laminated composite cylindrical shell in the transient heating case is much sharper than that in the steady state heating case. Therefore, the characteristics of nonuniformity of temperature gradient caused by the transient heating must be taken into account in analyzing the distribution of the temperature field for the laminated composite shells, especially for thick shells.
2. In the transient heating case for the laminated composite shell, the process of the heat conduction at the boundary points is quite different from that at internal points. The former proceeds upon two periods, that is, in the first period, the temperature variation rate with time is very rapid, then it becomes slow. However the later proceeds upon three periods, that is, slow-rapid-slow.
3. Although the nature of the interlaminar stress concentration in the vicinity of the free edge in the transient heating case is similar to that in the steady, the peak value of the interlaminar stresses and disturbed range caused by the effect of the free edge in the former are much larger than those in the later.
4. The effect of the transient heating has a localized behaviour, that is, the transient thermal interlaminar stresses are large, where the transient temperature gradient is large, and vice versa.
5. If the stacking sequence of the laminated composite shell is changed, the distribution of σ_z and τ_{xz} has an entirely different nature, hence the distribution of the interlaminar stresses depends on the stacking sequence of the laminated composite shells.

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